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RECOVERY OVARIAN ACTIVITY AFTER CALVING

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605323>**ANNOTATION**

New methods of reproduction biotechnology are introduced in modern technologies livestock. These methods help significantly increase profitability. Unfortunately, these methods are introduced slowly, since they require some initial costs. However, these same techniques can be used to increase reproductive ability of animals at competent use and understanding the essence of reproductive physiology and in traditional technology of reproduction.

Keywords: reproduction, follitropin, estrufalan, transplantation method, hormonal treatment, superovulation, postpartum.

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Азербайджан**ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ПОСЛЕ РОДОВ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В современных технологиях животноводства внедряются новые методы биотехнологии воспроизводства. Эти методы значительно помогают повысить рентабельность. К сожалению, эти методы внедряются медленно, поскольку требуют некоторых первоначальных затрат. Однако те же самые методики можно использовать для повышения репродуктивной способности животных при компетентном использовании и понимании сущности физиологии размножения и в традиционной технологии размножения.

Ключевые слова: воспроизводство, фолликулотропин, эструфалан, метод трансплантации, гормональное лечение, суперовуляция, послеродовой период.

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TUGISHDAN KEYINGI TUXUMDON FAOLIYATNING TIKLANISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy chorvachilik texnologiyalarida ko'payishning yangi biotexnologik usullari joriy etilmoqda. Bu usullar rentabellikni sezilarli darajada oshirishga yordam beradi. Afsuski, bu usullar dastlabki xarajatlarni talab qilganligi sababli sekin joriy etilmoqda. Biroq, ko'payish fiziologiyasining mohiyatini tushunish va kompetent foydalanish sharoitida shu usullardan an'anaviy ko'payish texnologiyalarida ham foydalanish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'payish, follitropin, estrofalan, transplantatsiya usuli, gormonal davolash, superovulyatsiya, tug'ilishdan keyingi davr.

Modern biotechnology methods involve the effects on animal organisms to stimulate physiological processes that increase economic value. One of these biotechnological methods is the transplantation of animal embryos [6;4]. To obtain embryos, the most productive cow suitable for the species is selected. At the same time, from a technological point of view, the process of embryo collection increases the calving interval [1,2]. If the embryo transplantation method is widely practiced, then some costs are inevitable due to the decrease in production economic indicators associated with the increased number of infertility days during the embryo stage of the cow [3].

In order to maintain the competitiveness of livestock enterprises, due to the strict requirements for production profitability, it is necessary to consider an economically justified scheme for incorporating embryo transplantation into the technological cycle of the enterprise [5]. The process of super ovulation induction and embryo collection must be regulated in such a way that the time between embryo collection and the first fertilization after calving is minimized. Most methods that do not take into account the requirements for economic efficiency can ensure this interval of at least 160 days [9].

Modern biotechnological tools and methods can reduce this period by 25-40 days [7,8]. The aim of this study was to investigate the possibility of reducing the interval between calving and the onset of ovarian cyclic activity in cows by using pharmacological agents, with the goal of starting to use the cow as an embryo donor at an earlier stage. Additionally, this technique is of great importance for veterinary specialists, as it helps reduce the calving interval using traditional reproduction technologies.

During the execution of the objectives, research was conducted in two directions: 1 - the possibilities for reducing the calving period before the first ovulation were determined; 2 - the effect of stimulating ovarian activity on the course of the first estrus cycles and ovarian function was clarified. In the first stage, the quality of reproduction was evaluated based on productivity indicators after artificial insemination in cows during the process of mono-ovulation. In the second stage, the indicators of embryo productivity were analyzed when cows were used as embryo donors. Various combinations of bio-regulators and regimes were used in the postpartum period. The studies were conducted on Holstein cows that had no more than 3-4 calves, with a milk yield of 4000-5000 kg per lactation, and feeding and care were the same for all groups. The most effective treatment schemes were those using the following drugs (Table 1).

Table 1.

The regimen of hormonal treatment for cows in the experimental groups.

Postpartum day.	Scheme 1.		Scheme 2.	
	Preparation.	Dose	Preparation.	Dose
11			BMZ	1000tv
12	Follitropin	1000tv		
	Estufalan	500mkq		
13			Superfan	500mkq
14	Surfaqon	15mkq		
15			superfan	15mkq

The use of both schemes is approximately equally effective and results in only small differences. In animals receiving these regimens, it was possible to accelerate the maturation of follicles compared to the control group. Thus, ovulation occurred with significantly better fertility indicators (Table 2).

Table 2.

The effectiveness of hormonal treatment for cows with and without the first ovulation by 16 days postpartum.

Group	Processing scheme	Number of animals	ovulation	General	After insemination	first service	Term of service	of ind ex
1 experienced	1	18	+	88,9	62	77	+20	1,6
2 experienced	2	23		100	70	67+	22	1,5
K control	--	22	+	91	56	68+	31	1,6
		28		100	71	66	+24	1,6
		13	+	92	50	91+	57	1,6
		15		100	56	82+	32	2,1

When treating animals with biostimulants according to the given schemes (including control animals), it is important to consider whether follicular growth, maturation, and ovulation occur by the 18th day postpartum. The presence of this factor leads to a decrease in reproductive performance. In such cases, a tendency was identified for the follicle to become a luteal cyst after undergoing follicular and then involution without additional intervention. This is likely related to the complete normalization of the endometrium and the uterine environment, which helps in the release of uterine prostaglandins adequate for the lysis of luteal tissue. In this situation, the duration of the estrous cycle is extended, and animals remain infertile for a longer period. This fact indicates that stimulating superovulation before the 18th day postpartum is unnecessary.

Many studies have proven that stimulating superovulation during the first and second estrous cycles postpartum is ineffective. We also found that the first cycle was shortened, and the first ovulation occurred 16-40 days after calving, with more than 45% of cows experiencing anestrus. Such ovulations were detected during regular rectal examinations of the ovaries in cows. When using these regimes to stimulate ovarian activity, acceptable results of superovulation were obtained during both the first (induced) and second estrous cycles. At the same time, the role of endocrine factors, which form the basis of reproductive activity in the early years, was clarified. The study of the hormonal profile helped identify the cause of the poor results of superovulation during the early postpartum period: this is due to the very low concentration of progesterone caused by the functional insufficiency of the corpus luteum on the 12th day of the cycle, as well as the incomplete recovery of the uterus and the overall reorganization of the cow's endocrine system after calving. However, the hormonal activation of ovarian structures allowed for relatively better (up to 8 viable embryos) but still acceptable superovulation results (ranging from 4 to 7 embryos) during the first (induced) and second estrous cycles. The level of progesterone in the blood of experimental animals was consistent with the levels in animals during the corresponding phase of their spontaneous estrous cycle, indicating the complete normalization of the reproductive system's function.

Thus, the study of the hormonal status of cows shows a certain degree of independence in ovarian function during the early postpartum period. This allows for earlier postpartum fertilization (in the classic reproduction system) and the implementation of biotechnological measures in the embryo transplantation system. Theoretically, it is important to clarify the difference in the speed of the restoration of cyclic processes in the ovaries, endometrium, and uterine environment. Moreover, the restoration processes occur most slowly in the uterus. Nevertheless, it is clear that stabilizing ovarian function through hormonal stimulation significantly accelerates the restoration processes in the uterine structures. This is confirmed by the improvement in the effectiveness of induced superovulation during the first and second estrous cycles postpartum in the animals.

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